

Supplemental information: Incomplete adaptation to surface movement during hand reaching

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We present results for models in Eq. 2-5 described in the main text, applied to the following error measures: maximum error, error at the midpoint of the trajectory (referred to as midpoint error), and error at the end of the trajectory (referred to as final error). In all cases, errors have a negative sign for points below the line connecting starting and target position, and a positive sign for those above.

Experiment 1

Supplementary Figure 1: Experiment 1, error over trials. Baseline, early perturbation, late perturbation, and washout blocks are represented in grey, light blue, dark blue, and orange, respectively. Data are binned by averaging the error across three consecutive trials. A. Maximum error. B. Midpoint error. C. Final error.

Supplementary Figure 2: Experiment 1, error distributions of the blocks used for fitting the models in Equations 2–5. Baseline, early perturbation, late perturbation, and washout blocks are represented in grey, light blue, dark blue, and orange, respectively. A. Maximum error. B. Midpoint error. C. Final error.

Model Eq. 2: Compare baseline and late perturbation trials

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
β_0	-0.592	0.518	72.327	-1.144	0.257
β_1	0.041	0.035	1849.118	1.200	0.230
$\beta_2 - \beta_0$	-1.933	0.657	86.095	-2.944	0.004
$\beta_3 - \beta_1$	-0.037	0.035	1849.065	-1.058	0.290

Supplementary

Table 1: Summary of model in Eq. 2 for maximum error, experiment 1.

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
β_0	-0.392	0.329	63.896	-1.192	0.238
β_1	0.001	0.021	1847.673	0.066	0.947
$\beta_2 - \beta_0$	-1.627	0.445	58.974	-3.656	0.001
$\beta_3 - \beta_1$	0.001	0.021	1847.624	0.043	0.966

Supplementary

Table 2: Summary of model in Eq. 2 for midpoint error, experiment 1.

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
β_0	-0.537	0.348	82.515	-1.542	0.127
β_1	0.005	0.024	1852.325	0.187	0.851
$\beta_2 - \beta_0$	0.009	0.396	234.078	0.022	0.983
$\beta_3 - \beta_1$	-0.005	0.024	1852.282	-0.205	0.838

Supplementary

Table 3: Summary of model in Eq. 2 for final error, experiment 1.

Model Eq. 3: Compare first perturbation trials with baseline, late perturbation trials

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
δ_0	-4.116	0.505	178.011	-8.149	< 0.001
$\delta_1 - \delta_0$	3.963	0.631	29.656	6.278	< 0.001
$\delta_2 - \delta_0$	2.093	0.712	23.165	2.939	0.007

Supplementary

Table 4: Summary of model in Eq. 3 for maximum error, experiment 1.

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
δ_0	-3.268	0.317	19.430	-10.302	< 0.001
$\delta_1 - \delta_0$	2.892	0.428	18.012	6.764	< 0.001
$\delta_2 - \delta_0$	1.493	0.428	18.585	3.487	0.003

Supplementary

Table 5: Summary of model in Eq. 3 for midpoint error, experiment 1.

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
δ_0	-0.575	0.482	18.014	-1.193	0.248
$\delta_1 - \delta_0$	0.091	0.405	39.834	0.225	0.823
$\delta_2 - \delta_0$	0.000	0.443	18.445	0.001	0.999

Supplementary

Table 6: Summary of model in Eq. 3 for final error, experiment 1.

Model Eq. 4: Catch trials

Supplementary Figure 3: Catch trials, ordered progressively from 1 to 10. The grey line represents the average error in the baseline block, while the orange line shows the mean error for the first three washout trials. A. Maximum error. B. Midpoint error. C. Final error.

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
ζ_0	1.998	0.736	18.294	2.715	0.014
ζ_1	0.082	0.126	17.487	0.651	0.524

Supplementary

Table 7: Summary of model in Eq. 4 for maximum error, experiment 1.

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
ζ_0	0.862	0.427	18.377	2.018	0.058
ζ_1	0.095	0.076	17.653	1.255	0.226

Supplementary

Table 8: Summary of model in Eq. 4 for midpoint error, experiment 1.

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
ζ_0	-0.650	0.455	28.014	-1.429	0.164
ζ_1	0.065	0.066	99.261	0.976	0.332

Supplementary

Table 9: Summary of model in Eq. 4 for final error, experiment 1.

Model Eq. 5: Compare baseline and early washout trials

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
η_0	-0.154	0.368	18.258	-0.420	0.679
$\eta_1 - \eta_0$	3.740	0.944	18.042	3.962	0.001

Supplementary Table 10: Summary of model in Eq. 5 for maximum error (early washout trials), experiment 1.

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
η_0	-0.374	0.239	18.168	-1.564	0.135
$\eta_1 - \eta_0$	2.583	0.546	17.981	4.728	< 0.001

Supplementary Table 11: Summary of model in Eq. 5 for midpoint error (early washout trials), experiment 1.

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
η_0	-0.474	0.234	17.559	-2.026	0.058
$\eta_1 - \eta_0$	0.566	0.665	18.070	0.851	0.406

Supplementary Table 12: Summary of model in Eq. 5 for final error (early washout trials), experiment 1.

Model Eq. 5: Compare baseline and late washout trials

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
η_0	-0.154	0.367	18.255	-0.419	0.680
$\eta_1 - \eta_0$	1.826	0.732	16.211	2.495	0.024

Supplementary Table 13: Summary of model in Eq. 5 for maximum error (late washout trials), experiment 1.

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
η_0	-0.375	0.239	18.160	-1.573	0.133
$\eta_1 - \eta_0$	1.235	0.412	17.373	3.002	0.008

Supplementary Table 14: Summary of model in Eq. 5 for midpoint error (late washout trials), experiment 1.

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
η_0	-0.474	0.234	17.543	-2.025	0.058
$\eta_1 - \eta_0$	1.494	0.602	19.054	2.481	0.023

Supplementary Table 15: Summary of model in Eq. 5 for final error (late washout trials), experiment 1.

Experiment 2

Supplementary Figure 4: Experiment 2, error over trials. Baseline, early perturbation, late perturbation, and washout blocks are represented in grey, light blue, dark blue, and orange, respectively. Data are binned by averaging the error across three consecutive trials. A. Maximum error. B. Midpoint error. C. Final error.

Supplementary Figure 5: Experiment 2, error distributions of the blocks used for fitting the models in Equations 2–5. Baseline, early perturbation, late perturbation, and washout blocks are represented in grey, light blue, dark blue, and orange, respectively. A. Maximum error. B. Midpoint error. C. Final error.

Model Eq. 2: Compare baseline and late perturbation trials

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
β_0	-3.545	2.635	22.489	-1.345	0.192
β_1	-0.029	0.084	1703.312	-0.346	0.730
$\beta_2 - \beta_0$	-19.043	3.105	24.934	-6.134	< 0.001
$\beta_3 - \beta_1$	0.052	0.084	1703.288	0.616	0.538

Supplementary

Table 16: Summary of model in Eq. 2 for maximum error, experiment 2.

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
β_0	-2.493	1.414	21.806	-1.763	0.092
β_1	0.008	0.042	1703.070	0.187	0.852
$\beta_2 - \beta_0$	-8.064	1.691	23.545	-4.770	< 0.001
$\beta_3 - \beta_1$	-0.003	0.042	1703.050	-0.078	0.938

Supplementary

Table 17: Summary of model in Eq. 2 for midpoint error, experiment 2.

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
β_0	-6.485	3.517	21.382	-1.844	0.079
β_1	0.099	0.098	1703.012	1.010	0.313
$\beta_2 - \beta_0$	-18.279	3.712	24.713	-4.925	< 0.001
$\beta_3 - \beta_1$	-0.083	0.099	1702.992	-0.834	0.404

Supplementary

Table 18: Summary of model in Eq. 2 for final error, experiment 2.

Model Eq. 3: Compare first perturbation trials with baseline, late perturbation trials

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
δ_0	-20.272	3.771	18.007	-5.376	< 0.001
$\delta_1 - \delta_0$	16.432	2.900	16.996	5.667	< 0.001
$\delta_2 - \delta_0$	0.098	2.506	19.250	0.039	0.969

Supplementary

Table 19: Summary of model in Eq. 3 for maximum error, experiment 2.

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
δ_0	-8.652	1.606	18.123	-5.389	< 0.001
$\delta_1 - \delta_0$	6.242	1.115	15.501	5.598	< 0.001
$\delta_2 - \delta_0$	-1.423	1.237	19.295	-1.151	0.264

Supplementary

Table 20: Summary of model in Eq. 3 for midpoint error, experiment 2.

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
δ_0	-20.530	4.058	18.073	-5.059	< 0.001
$\delta_1 - \delta_0$	15.073	3.168	16.700	4.757	< 0.001
$\delta_2 - \delta_0$	-2.447	3.098	19.140	-0.790	0.439

Supplementary

Table 21: Summary of model in Eq. 3 for final error, experiment 2.

Model Eq. 4: Catch trials

Supplementary Figure 6: Catch trials, ordered progressively from 1 to 10. The grey line represents the average error in the baseline block, while the orange line shows the mean error for the first three washout trials. A. Maximum error. B. Midpoint error. C. Final error.

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
ζ_0	-7.218	4.070	15.358	-1.774	0.096
ζ_1	0.112	0.388	17.448	0.289	0.776

Supplementary

Table 22: Summary of model in Eq. 4 for maximum error, experiment 2.

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
ζ_0	-4.424	2.312	16.637	-1.913	0.073
ζ_1	0.035	0.199	18.928	0.176	0.862

Supplementary

Table 23: Summary of model in Eq. 4 for midpoint error, experiment 2.

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
ζ_0	-9.451	4.804	16.206	-1.967	0.067
ζ_1	0.229	0.506	18.818	0.452	0.656

Supplementary

Table 24: Summary of model in Eq. 4 for final error, experiment 2.

Model Eq. 5: Compare baseline and early washout trials

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
η_0	-3.847	2.492	17.972	-1.544	0.140
$\eta_1 - \eta_0$	-3.354	2.916	12.476	-1.150	0.272

Supplementary Table 25: Summary of model in Eq. 5 for maximum error (early washout trials), experiment 2.

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
η_0	-2.415	1.347	17.979	-1.793	0.090
$\eta_1 - \eta_0$	-2.036	2.061	12.032	-0.988	0.343

Supplementary Table 26: Summary of model in Eq. 5 for midpoint error (first washout trials), experiment 2.

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
η_0	-5.470	3.364	17.992	-1.626	0.121
$\eta_1 - \eta_0$	-4.656	4.609	12.906	-1.010	0.331

Supplementary Table 27: Summary of model in Eq. 5 for final error (first washout trials), experiment 2.

Model Eq. 5: Compare baseline and late washout trials

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
η_0	-3.842	2.491	17.972	-1.542	0.141
$\eta_1 - \eta_0$	-0.568	3.137	17.035	-0.181	0.859

Supplementary Table 28: Summary of model in Eq. 5 for maximum error (last washout trials), experiment 2.

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
η_0	-2.413	1.347	17.979	-1.791	0.090
$\eta_1 - \eta_0$	-1.377	1.351	17.238	-1.019	0.322

Supplementary Table 29: Summary of model in Eq. 5 for midpoint error (last washout trials), experiment 2.

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
η_0	-5.463	3.363	17.993	-1.624	0.122
$\eta_1 - \eta_0$	-1.416	4.324	16.815	-0.327	0.747

Supplementary Table 30: Summary of model in Eq. 5 for final error (last washout trials), experiment 2.

Bayesian analysis

Supplementary Figure 7: Posterior estimates and 95% credible intervals for parameters in Experiment 1 under different prior distributions (mean = 0; variances = 0.5, 1, 5, 10). The red lines represent parameter estimates calculated with LMMS, with red shaded areas indicating 95% confidence intervals. A. Difference between the first and last 90 perturbed trials (Eq. 3). B. Intercept for progressively ordered catch trials (Eq. 4). C. Slope for progressively ordered catch trials (Eq. 4). D. Difference between baseline and first washout trials (Eq. 5).

Supplementary Figure 8: Posterior estimates and 95% credible intervals for parameters in Experiment 2 under different prior distributions (mean = 0; variances = 0.5, 1, 5, 10). The red lines represent parameter estimates calculated with LMMs, with red shaded areas indicating 95% confidence intervals. A. Difference between the first and last 90 perturbed trials (Eq. 3). B. Intercept for progressively ordered catch trials (Eq. 4). C. Slope for progressively ordered catch trials (Eq. 4). D. Difference between baseline and first washout trials (Eq. 5).

Path length

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
θ_0	67.289	1.056	26.902	63.717	< 0.001
θ_1	-0.010	0.013	19.673	-0.775	0.448
$\theta_{2, \text{early pert.}}$	0.385	0.609	2932.978	0.632	0.528
$\theta_{2, \text{late pert.}}$	-0.431	0.540	2932.939	-0.797	0.426
$\theta_{2, \text{catch}}$	-0.942	0.841	2932.966	-1.120	0.263
$\theta_{2, \text{washout}}$	-1.878	0.691	2932.889	-2.718	0.007

Supplementary

Table 31: Summary of model in Eq. 6 for path length, Experiment 1.

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
θ_0	58.019	2.341	16.293	24.782	< 0.001
θ_1	0.006	0.018	10.910	0.332	0.746
$\theta_{2, \text{early pert.}}$	11.084	0.732	2672.539	15.146	< 0.001
$\theta_{2, \text{late pert.}}$	8.650	0.641	2672.530	13.500	< 0.001
$\theta_{2, \text{catch}}$	2.868	1.038	2672.492	2.763	0.006
$\theta_{2, \text{washout}}$	-1.234	0.840	2672.543	-1.469	0.142

Supplementary

Table 32: Summary of model in Eq. 6 for path length, Experiment 2.

Tangential forces

Force peak along x

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
θ_0	0.198	0.023	18.072	8.452	< 0.001
θ_1	0.001	0.001	13.481	1.573	0.139
$\theta_{2, \text{early pert.}}$	-0.123	0.012	2933.437	-10.034	< 0.001
$\theta_{2, \text{late pert.}}$	-0.092	0.011	2933.335	-8.438	< 0.001
$\theta_{2, \text{catch}}$	0.078	0.017	2933.423	4.607	< 0.001
$\theta_{2, \text{washout}}$	0.190	0.014	2933.159	13.636	< 0.001

Supplementary Table 33: Summary of model in Eq. 6 for tangential forces along x, Experiment 1.

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
θ_0	0.234	0.022	7.812	10.602	< 0.001
θ_1	0.000	0.000	12.278	1.035	0.321
$\theta_{2, \text{early pert.}}$	-0.065	0.008	2678.490	-7.708	< 0.001
$\theta_{2, \text{late pert.}}$	-0.071	0.007	2678.447	-9.680	< 0.001
$\theta_{2, \text{catch}}$	-0.001	0.012	2678.369	-0.100	0.921
$\theta_{2, \text{washout}}$	0.078	0.010	2678.478	8.068	< 0.001

Supplementary Table 34: Summary of model in Eq. 6 for tangential forces along x, Experiment 2.

Force peak along y

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
θ_0	0.048	0.052	14.993	0.931	0.367
θ_1	0.002	0.001	14.707	2.473	0.026
$\theta_{2, \text{early pert.}}$	0.264	0.013	2932.599	20.461	< 0.001
$\theta_{2, \text{late pert.}}$	0.349	0.011	2932.581	30.589	< 0.001
$\theta_{2, \text{catch}}$	0.120	0.018	2932.595	6.744	< 0.001
$\theta_{2, \text{washout}}$	0.240	0.015	2932.554	16.441	< 0.001

Supplementary Table 35: Summary of model in Eq. 6 for tangential forces along y, Experiment 1.

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
θ_0	0.104	0.061	3.266	1.704	0.179
θ_1	0.000	0.000	6.839	0.995	0.354
$\theta_{2, \text{early pert.}}$	0.126	0.012	2675.552	10.409	< 0.001
$\theta_{2, \text{late pert.}}$	0.156	0.011	2675.514	14.789	< 0.001
$\theta_{2, \text{catch}}$	-0.013	0.017	2675.485	-0.776	0.438
$\theta_{2, \text{washout}}$	0.104	0.014	2675.528	7.509	< 0.001

Supplementary Table 36: Summary of model in Eq. 6 for tangential forces along y, Experiment 2.